

Predicting Multiple Parkinson's Disease Tremor Categories Using Advanced Neural Network Models

Minakshi Rajput
IICT, MGM University
mrajput@mgmu.ac.in

Smita Ponde
IICT, MGM University
sponde@mgmu.ac.in

Monika Gangapurwala
IICT, MGM University
mgangapurwala@mgmu.ac.in

A. Selvaraj
IICT, MGM University
aselvaraj@mgmu.ac.in

Sharvari Tamane
IICT, MGM University
hodudict@mgmu.ac.in

Abstract

Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder in which tremor is one of the most prevalent and clinically relevant motor symptoms. Early and accurate detection of different tremor types enables improved disease monitoring and personalized treatment. This work presents a Deep-learning-based framework for multi-label classification of tremor subtypes using the ALAMEDA_PD_tremor_dataset. We implemented three different neural networks namely, 1. Feed Forward Neural Network, 2. Patternnet 3. Deep Neural Network. Multi-label predictions were generated using a one-vs-all strategy, and model performance was assessed using Hamming loss, accuracy, confusion matrices, and regression diagnostics. The proposed Deep neural-network model achieved a multi-label accuracy of approximately 89%, demonstrating reliable discrimination between tremor classes despite inter-patient variability and overlapping symptom expression.

Keywords: Parkinson's Disease, Neural network, Deep Learning, Feed forward neural network

1. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a chronic neurodegenerative disorder affecting more than 10 million individuals worldwide. Among its motor symptoms, tremor is one of the earliest, most visible, and most clinically informative indicators of disease progression. Traditional tremor assessment relies on clinical observations, such as the MDS-UPDRS (Movement Disorder Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale), which is time-consuming, subjective, and limited to episodic clinical visits.

Wearable sensors, particularly wrist-worn accelerometers, enable continuous, objective, and quantitative tremor monitoring. Modern machine-learning methods can leverage sensor-derived features to automate tremor recognition, classify tremor subtypes, and reduce clinician burden. However, tremor expression in PD is complex: an individual may simultaneously exhibit multiple tremor types (rest tremor, postural tremor, kinetic tremor, constancy-of-rest tremor). This creates a multi-label classification problem, where more than one label can be positive for a single patient. Previous studies show that many

researchers implemented Machine learning and Deep learning methods to classify tremor type of PD patients.

Aditi Govindua, Sushila Palwe classified Parkinson's patient audio data using different ML methods such as KNN, logistic regression, random forest regression and SVM . They achieved an accuracy of 91.83% and sensitivity of 0.95 for kNN [3]. Jiayu Zhang et al. experimented on PPMI dataset consisting of demographic variables, hospital admission examinations, clinical assessment, and polygenic risk score. They found that penalized logistic regression and XGBoost were the most accurate algorithms for assessing PD risk [4]. Aleksei Shcherbak et al. have experimented on a dataset consisting of data of 113 people. Their approach was based on wearable sensors and machine learning to differentiate healthy controls from patients with stages 1 and 2 PD. They achieved f1-micro scores of 0.78 and 0.88 for PD stages 1 and 2, respectively [5]. Gallo-Aristizabal et al. proposed two different approaches one was based on CNN and another one was based on hand-crafted features which are pressure and kinematic measurements which are measured by time series. They concluded that dynamic approaches are the best way to indicate PD related symptoms. They achieved the highest accuracy for pressure-based handwriting features [6].

C. R. Pereira et al. identified PD using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), which learns features which are extracted from smart pens given during the individual's exam. The smart pen accompanied with sensors collects the features from handwritten dynamics. They additionally created a database of these features to support upcoming research in this area [7]. Kotsavasiloglou, C., et al. experimented on their own dataset of 44 subjects. They computed various features like the pen tip's velocity, the deviation from the horizontal plane, and the trajectory's entropy and differentiated between healthy and PD persons with an accuracy of 91% using Naïve Bayes ML classifier [8].

RN Rees et al. listed various benefits of early Diagnosis over timely diagnosis of Parkinson's disease [9]. Huang, G H, et al. experimented on a brain MRI dataset of 202 persons consisting of 196 PD persons and 6 healthy persons. They achieved the highest accuracy for VGG deep neural pretrained network over machine learning classifiers [10]. Nilashi, Mehrbakhsh, et al. predicted UPDRS score (Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale) by analyzing the speech signal properties. This proposed method was found effective in PD progression for early prediction accuracy and thus reducing computation time [11].

In their study, Talitckii, Aleksandr, et al. included 41 PD patients and 15 patients with other neurodegenerative diseases. They found that considering bradykinesia and tremor together, the accuracy of distinguishing PD from similar diseases increases (f1 score 0.88) [12]. Basil K Varghese et al. experimented on Parkinson's Tele monitoring dataset. Authors predicted the motor and total UPDRS scores using different ML methods [13].

Dadu A et al. used data from the Parkinson's Disease Progression Marker Initiative (n = 294) to identify patient subtypes and predict disease progression. They classified PD progression into three categories: slow, moderate, and fast [14]. Tahedl M et al. successfully distinguished between the two motor subtypes of Parkinson's disease namely, 1. tremor-dominant (PD-TD) and 2. postural instability/gait difficulty (PD-PIGD) using a deep learning model that achieved an AUC of 0.972 [15].

The proposed research uses the ALAMEDA_PD_tremor_dataset to develop and evaluate Neural network models for identifying PD tremor subtypes from preprocessed accelerometer

features. The study compares these neural network models using performance parameters like Overall multilabel Classification Accuracy and Hamming Loss.

2. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The ALAMEDA tremor dataset contains 99 columns and multiple patient sessions. Each row in the dataset represents one patient/sample. The dataset has metadata for the first three columns, which are mainly: 1. start_timestamp, 2. end_timestamp and 3. subject_id. The next 92 columns are feature columns. These features are engineered from triaxial accelerometer signals collected via GENEActiv wearables during a 30-minute clinical MDS-UPDRS assessment. The raw accelerometer signals are first band-pass filtered between 2.5 and 12.5 Hz to isolate the frequency range associated with Parkinson tremor. To reduce dependency on sensor orientation and placement, the magnitude of the filtered signals and the first principal component (PC1) are then computed. The processed signals are subsequently divided into overlapping time windows of 2048 samples (approximately 20.48 seconds) with a 50% overlap to ensure continuity and capture transient tremor characteristics. From each window, a total of 92 features are extracted across both time and frequency domains, with spectral features obtained after applying a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). Few of these features are Mean, variance, RMS, Zero-crossing rate, Entropy, Power spectral density, Peak frequencies, FFT coefficients, Energy in defined tremor frequency bands.

The last 4 columns which are categorical labels indicating type of Parkinson's disease. These are Constancy_of_rest (Rest tremor consistency), Kinetic_tremor (Tremor during movement), Postural_tremor (Tremor while maintaining posture), and Rest_tremor (Classic PD rest tremor). The main aim is to predict which Parkinson subtype a patient has based on their measured features.

The last 4 columns are derived from UPDRS-III clinician-annotated scores and binarised as : 0 → absence of tremor, 1 → presence of tremor. This particular problem is a multi-label classification problem, where each patient may have multiple tremor types active.

3. METHODOLOGY

Data preprocessing, involving feature scaling or normalization, is performed prior to training. The dataset is subsequently split into 80% for training and 20% for testing. All experimental procedures are executed using MATLAB 2020a. For experimental purposes, we trained three different neural networks on the training dataset: (1) a feedforward neural network, (2) a PatternNet model, and (3) a deep neural network.

a) Implementation using feedforward neural network

We started with a feedforward neural network which is capable of capturing complex patterns. A feedforward neural network is a type of artificial neural network in which information flows strictly in one direction from the input layer, through one or more hidden layers, to the output layer without any recurrent or feedback connections. The implemented network consisted of an input layer corresponding to the number of extracted features,

followed by two fully connected hidden layers that applied nonlinear activation functions (ReLU) to learn complex relationships within the data.

Dropout regularization was incorporated within the hidden layers to mitigate overfitting and improve generalization. The final fully connected output layer contained four neurons corresponding to the four tremor-related labels. A regression layer was used at the output to support multi-label learning, allowing the network to independently estimate the probability of each tremor type. During prediction, a threshold of 0.5 was applied to convert these continuous outputs into binary label decisions. Figure 1 shows Feed-forward architecture details for experimentation.

Figure 1. Feed-forward architecture details for experimentation

As it is a multi-label classification problem where each person can have multiple labels (tremor types) simultaneously. This network outputs 4 binary predictions at once. This single model learns all labels jointly and can capture correlations among Parkinson subtypes.

b) Implementation using patternNet

Next we have implemented a patternnet which is a MATLAB's feedforward neural network designed specifically for pattern recognition (classification) tasks. It is basically a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) pre-configured for classification tasks.

Hidden layer size has increased from 10, 15 to 20. And results are noted. We also used different activation functions like Hyperbolic Tangent Sigmoid in Hidden Layer and Logistic Sigmoid in Output Layer. Activation functions introduce nonlinearity into a neural network. Without them, a network behaves like a simple linear regression model regardless of how many layers it has. They allow the network to Learn complex relationships in data and also captures high-dimensional correlations between features

The use of Hyperbolic Tangent Sigmoid in the hidden layers introduces nonlinear, zero-centered transformations that enhance learning and accelerate convergence, making the network effective at capturing complex patterns in the 92-dimensional accelerometer feature space. The Logistic Sigmoid activation in the output layer transforms the network's outputs into probability values bounded between 0 and 1, making it ideal for multi-label binary classification where each tremor type must be predicted independently. Predicted output is thresholded at 0.5 to convert probabilities to labels.

Figure 2. patternnet architecture details for experimentation

c) Implementation using Deep feed forward multi label neural network

The Deep neural network we selected for experimentation consists of two hidden fully connected layers with 64 and 32 neurons, each followed by ReLU activation and dropout regularization (0.3 and 0.2, respectively) to prevent overfitting. A final fully connected layer with four neurons maps the learned representation to the four tremor-related labels. Sigmoid activation is applied to produce independent probability estimates for each label, which is appropriate for multi-label classification. The model is trained using the Adam optimizer for 150 epochs with a minibatch size of 32. The regression output layer enables the network to learn continuous probability values between 0 and 1, which are thresholded at 0.5 during prediction.

Figure 3. Deep Feed forward neural network details for implementation

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We assessed the performance of all the above models using two evaluation metrics: (1) Overall Accuracy and (2) Hamming Loss.

1. **Overall Accuracy:** It measures the percentage of samples for which all predicted labels exactly match all true labels. A sample is counted as “correct” only if every label is predicted correctly. We computed Overall accuracy as shown in Equation 1, where,

y_i = true label vector for sample

\hat{y}_i = predicted label vector

N = number of samples

$$\text{Overall Accuracy} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i) \text{ ---Eq. (1)}$$

2. **Hamming Loss:** It is a very important evaluation parameter in case of multi-label classification problems. It measures how many labels the model incorrectly predicted, independently for each label. This metric is suitable for multi-label classification since a sample may have several correct labels, and Hamming Loss measures errors on a per-label basis rather than evaluating the full label set at once. The metric ranges from 0 to 1, with 0 representing perfect predictions and 1 representing entirely incorrect predictions. Hamming Loss is calculated as shown in Equation 2, where ‘N’ is the number of samples and ‘L’ is the number of labels.

$y_{i,j}$ = true value of label j for sample i

$\hat{y}_{i,j}$ = predicted value (0 or 1 after thresholding)

$$\text{Hamming Loss} = \frac{1}{N \times L} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^L (y_{i,j} + \hat{y}_{i,j}) \text{ ---Eq. (2)}$$

Table 1 summarizes the Accuracy and Hamming Loss obtained for the various neural network models.

Table 1. Accuracies and Hamming Losses for Various Neural Networks

Type of Network	No. of hidden layers	Overall Accuracy	Hamming loss
Feed forward NN	1	0.2733	0.7267
PatternNet	8	0.74127	0.25873
PatternNet	10	0.7512	0.2488
PatternNet with activation functions	10	0.7497	0.2503
PatternNet	15	0.73645	0.26355
PatternNet	20	0.73946	0.26054
Deep Neural Network	2	0.89096	0.10904

In addition to these two metrics, we further evaluated the performance of the implemented neural networks using error histograms, training gradient analysis, training performance curves.

Error Histogram: Using error histograms we can visualise the distribution of prediction errors. Error can be computed as Equation 3.

$$e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i \text{---Eq.(3)}$$

As shown in figure 4, the bottom rightmost error graph which is obtained for Deep neural networks is the best as the blue bars (training), green (validation), and red (test) are almost completely clustered around zero error. This indicates that the network's predictions are extremely close to the true target values for most samples.

Figure 4. Error Histograms

Figure 5 shows the training performance graphs of various neural networks. The bottom left graph shows the best model of deep neural network with lowest validation cross-entropy of 0.31387.

Figure 5. Validation Performance of PatternNet for different hidden layers (a) Hidden layers = 15 (b) Hidden layers = 8 (c) Hidden layers = 20 (d) Training Performance of plot of Deep Neural Network

Figure 6. Neural Network Training state Plot of Deep Neural Network

Figure 6 shows how the gradient decreases over time. It also shows different parameter's behaviour like Mu (μ) - damping parameter, Number of parameters (gamk), Sum-squared parameters (ssX), Validation checks (val fail) etc. over number of epochs.

Figure 7. Training Gradient Evolution and Early Stopping Behavior of Patternnet during Learning

The graphs in figure 7 demonstrate the convergence characteristics and early stopping behavior of the trained neural network. The gradient curve shows a steady decrease from high initial values to approximately 0.02, indicating that the learning process is stabilizing as the network approaches an optimal solution. Meanwhile, the validation checks plot reveals that the validation loss begins to rise after epoch 45, triggering a sequence of validation failures. When the number of validation failures reaches the preset limit of six, the early stopping mechanism halts training at epoch 53. This prevents overfitting and ensures the model parameters are taken from the epoch that produced the best validation performance. Together, the plots confirm that the network trained efficiently, converged properly, and stopped at the appropriate time to maintain generalization performance.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

This study presented a comprehensive deep-learning framework for predicting multiple Parkinson's disease tremor subtypes using wearable-sensor data from the ALAMEDA_PD_tremor_dataset. Three neural-network architectures namely Feedforward NN, PatternNet, and a deeper feedforward model were trained and evaluated using accuracy, Hamming loss, error histograms, and detailed training-state diagnostics. Among the models tested, the Deep Feedforward Multi-Label Network exhibited the strongest performance, achieving an overall multi-label accuracy of 89% and hamming loss of 10%.

Several opportunities exist to expand the present work. First, integrating raw waveform-based deep models such as 1D-CNNs, LSTMs, or transformer architectures may further enhance performance by eliminating manual feature engineering and capturing temporal tremor dynamics more directly.

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